

LINGUISTIC AND DIDACTIC FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION

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Annotation

Linguistics is a comprehensive topic studied by many linguists. Based on their scientific and practical opinions, many linguists gave different definitions, taking into account the dependence of other sciences on linguistics, their similarities and differences. It is defined as linguomethodology in some scholars' work. However, there is a huge difference between linguodidactics and linguomethodology. Both of terms play a crucial role in improving foreign languages pronunciation, it is essential to investigate phonetics and its articulatory difficulties.

Keywords:

linguodidactics, didaktikos, linguomethodology, didactology, supersegmental units, phonologists, inlaut, auslaut, anlaut, phologists.

Linguodidactics is derived from the Latin words lingua- "language" and Greek "didaktikos"- "teaching", and is a science dealing with the creation of a general theory of language teaching. This term was first introduced to science by the Russian linguists. It was introduced by Shansky, who emphasizes that this science is intended to study the problems of language education. [Ismailova B. 2015, 53-b].

In a general sense, the term linguodidactics refers to the analysis of the goals of language teaching, as well as the concepts of studying the theoretical and methodological problems of language teaching [M.Djusupov. 2009, p. 27]. Because it includes many parts of the training process, for example, theoretical and practical methods, teaching goals are somewhat confused with the tasks of methodological science. The term linguomethodology, which is synonymous with the concepts of linguodidactics and methodology, is also used in scientific research. "Linguomethodology" explains this term in his book "Словарь – справочник по методике русского языка " М.Р. Lvov - it is a method of teaching the mother tongue or a foreign language, this term is often used in

linguodidactic articles and in the methodology of teaching the Russian language in national schools is used" [Lviv. 1988, p. 96].

V. M. Beldiyan , first of all, used the term didactolinguistics in a similar sense to the word linguodidactics [Beldiyan. 1980,21-b], and later used only the term didactology. It is not difficult to find out here that the scientist meant teaching and education, that is, the theory of education (didactics) is primary, and language is secondary, because didactics refers to the subjects taught in all secondary and higher educational institutions (sciences) have an equal relationship [Ismailova B. 2015, p. 54].

In our next example, V. M. Beldiyan mentions that he used the terms linguadidactics and didactic science interchangeably, but later found out that they were different. In the current state of science, new scientific directions formed at the junction of sciences become an independent field of science, and this process is realized due to the integral connection of a new scientific direction or scientific field within a single discipline with other sciences (relative or not related). Many such processes are observed. In particular, the 20th century was a period in which many new sciences were formed in a natural state. For example, as a result of interaction between language levels and stylistics, a number of linguistic-scientific directions, collectively known as stylistics of levels or stylistics of sources, have emerged. [M. Djusupov. 2009, p.137].

The effective use of laws and methods of linguodidactics and methodology in teaching English to students of the Uzbek audience is the shortest way to achieve the intended goal [Ismailova.B. 2015, p. 58]. For good linguadidactics and methodology in the uzbek audience, what are the tasks and goals of teaching English language , especially the pronunciation layer?

Phonetics is the beauty of foreign language knowledge and skills. Any acquired knowledge shows its appearance only with correct and fluent pronunciation. In this regard, the question arises as to what kind of field and what kind of object, purpose and aspects phonetics has. The object of phonetics is the sound side of the language, phonetic construction. The sound side of the language includes units such as speech sounds, syllables, accent, tone (intonation, melody). The purpose of phonetics is to study the physical-acoustic, anatomical-physiological and linguistic-functional bases of phonetic units, to determine their role in language. Such a goal determines its following tasks: a) to study the laws of formation of units, such as sound, accent, melody; b) to familiarize students with the above laws and scientific and theoretical ideas

related to these laws; d) identifying controversial issues related to the phonetic-phonological system, reacting to them; e) formation of phonetic analysis skills among students; f) to give students brief information about phonetists-phonologists who worked in this field. [H. Jamolkhanov. 2005, page 18]

The functions of phonetic units in the language are as follows:

1) formative function: (Russian - образующая функция). This implies the participation of phonetic units in the composition of words or morphemes or as building material in the structure of sentences and speech. Supersegmental units such as tone, melody, and pause participate in the construction of a sentence or in the composition of a speech as a special phenomenon: the specific intonations of sentences, interrogatives, and commands, as well as intonations in poetic verses are examples of this;

2) identifying function (Russian: опознавательная функция). It is observed that the phonetic units in the phonetic vocabulary serve to "recognize" and "remember" the word and its meaning: the meaning of the word (or the meaning of the morpheme) remains in the human memory depending on the phonetic form of the word (or the morpheme). Considering that most words are phonetically different from each other, it is also possible that such differences are used to differentiate their meanings. Therefore, words and grammatical forms gain information in speech due to their sound matter. The sound alone makes the word or word form meaningful to the listener. [H. Jamolkhanov. 2005, page 19].

So, if we pay attention to the linguistic didactic principles of teaching English pronunciation, we should also dwell on the concept of the content of teaching pronunciation. All the phonetic material in the studied foreign language is divided into two groups - pronunciation units that are mandatory to learn during the educational process and pronunciation phenomena that are not mandatory to learn in the educational conditions. "Mandatory" pronunciation minimum, in turn, is further divided into two groups, the first group is units for which pronunciation training is considered a condition, the second is pronunciation units that do not require special exercises. The first group of units is the content of teaching pronunciation. E.g. English (German) sound [tj] is not difficult for Russian, Tajik and Uzbek students, because this sound is a phenomenon that exists in the pronunciation norm of the native language, that is, in the student's linguistic experience. Kazakh nationality is a very difficult unit for foreign language learners, because it is foreign to the pronunciation of their native language. As can be seen from the examples, the foreign language

pronunciation minimum is the same for all schools, but based on the students' language experience, the content of teaching pronunciation is formed separately for different learning stages. The content of teaching pronunciation of a foreign language is usually - "It is determined as a result of comparing the phonetic systems of the languages that come into contact in the minds of students, studying the mistakes of students, creating a typology of difficulties [J. Jalolov. 2015, p. 71].

So, what are the difficulties that learners may face in this regard, and what solutions should we find to overcome them? In the science of foreign language methodology, the types of pronunciation difficulties are classified as follows:

1. Articulatory difficulty that occurs in the individual pronunciation of a sound.
2. If two sounds (or combinations of sounds that cause alternative associations with each other) are confused (for example, long and short, voiced and unvoiced), then an oppositional difficulty occurs.
3. When the sounds are at the beginning (anlaut), in the middle (inlaut) and at the end (auslaut) of the word, or when they are adjacent to each other, there is a certain difficulty of pronunciation - positional difficulties. For example, consonants at the end and beginning of words (two or more side by side) are extremely difficult for Uzbek students.
4. Difficulties in differentiating sounds occur during hearing perception, they are called acoustic difficulties (J. Jalolov. 1996, p. 78).

From the above points, it can be concluded that pronunciation difficulties are not considered as a separate problem or a separate year is not spent to eliminate pronunciation difficulties, but it finds its solutions together with the learning stages of vocabulary and grammar.

References:

1. Ismailova B.Y. O'zbek auditoriyasida birinchi kurs studentlarini ingliz tilining konsonantizmiga o'rgatishning lingvodidaktik asoslari, Toshkent, 2015.
2. Jalolov.J.J. Chet til o'qitish metodikasi, Toshkent, 2012.
3. Jamolxonov.H. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili, Toshkent, 2015.
4. Бельдиян В.М. Научно-методические проблемы обучения фонетике современного русского языка студентов национальных групп (опыт системного анализа).-Т., 1980.
5. Жалолов Ж.Ж. Чет тил ўғитиш методикаси. -Т., 1996.
6. Джусупов М. Лингводидактика и методика в полинаучной системе языкового образования. //Русский язык за рубежом, 2009, № 2, 26-32-б.